

SECReTOUR
Sustainable Creative Tourism

Sustainable Business Models, Tourism and Cultural Heritage

Shall we get organised?

Salar, Granada

15/01/2026

Organized by:

UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA

In collaboration with:

Workshop structure

WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

WHY ARE WE HERE? WHAT WE WANT TO DO?

You have mentioned:

What motivates you to participate in this workshop and what would you like to learn, discuss or take away from it?

- Learn about alternative business models
- Practical tools for developing tourism in Salar
- Exchange ideas with other residents
- Learn from successful experiences in contexts similar to Salar
- Learn about mechanisms for involving the local population in tourism potential

You have spoken

Thinking about Salar's future, what are you most interested in exploring in the workshop?

24 answers

Common goal

1

Common language:

Business models,
Governance,
Heritage
communitiy

2

**From theory to
practice:**

Let's apply these
concepts to the
town's tourism
development

3

Let's get started:

a roadmpa for
action and defined
roles

BUSINESS MODELS

Why are we interested in talking about business models?

A brief introduction: Business Models

What is it?

A flexible tool to
better understand
your project

Traditionally
focused on the
business world

The value
generated takes
new meanings

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSITION	RELATIONSHIP WITH CUSTOMERS/BENEFICIARIES	CUSTOMERS/BENEFICIARY SGMENTS
<p>What individuals, groups, or institutions are essential for this to work?</p>				
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p>		<p>PROMOTION/DISSEMINATION CHANNELS</p>	
	<p>What resources does our project have that are essential to its functioning?</p>			
<p>EXPENSE STRUCTURE</p>		<p>SOURCES OF INCOME</p>		
<p>Where are we going to spend money?</p>				

Brief introduction: Business Model:

What is it used for?

Improve
communication

Define what is
being offered, to
whom, how, and
for what purpose

Organise the
internal
structure

Facilitate decision-
making and
innovation

Alternative business models?

Integrating the sustainability component

Cultural Business Models

General Characteristics

Heritage as a **resource**: the importance of origin. Our Roman Villa

Strong **sense** of cultural **identity**. I am from **Salar**.

Complex by nature: a **mosaic**. **Institutions and individuals who care for heritage**

TOURISM, MASIVE OR SUSTAINABLE?

Why are we interested in discussing business models?

*Is this what we want for Salar?
What can we do about it?*

Heritage Communities

A common framework

Network of people who value certain elements of cultural heritage and wish to preserve and pass them on, and use them for the socio-economic development of the community, for example through tourism.

Heritage communities

Your role

“There is a growing awareness that the long-term positive effects of tourism depend largely on the participation of local communities, which are not mere spectators of development, but active agents that face and evolve alongside the challenges associated with tourism development.”

Source Movono & Becken, 2018, citado en Dahles et al., 2020, p. 820

An example in Spain

Projecto Patrimoni de la Universitat Jaume I, Castellón

“Network of heritage communities working together to care for and value their heritage”

TODAY

TWO YEARS FROM NOW

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

Group 4

	INTERNAL	EXTERNAL
NEGATIVE	S Strengths	W Weaknesses
POSITIVE	O Opportunities	T Threats

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From theory to practise

Examples of success in sustainable tourism

Types of alternative business models focused on tourism

Catalysts for socio-economic and cultural development?

Participatory Governance

- *Mancomunidad Taula del Sénia, Valencia-Cataluña-Aragón*
- *Swansea Bay, Gales*

Ecomuseums and Digital Tools Social

- *Comuniterràe, Piamonte*

Social Entrepreneurship

- *Cooperative La Paranza, Nápoles*

Product-Service System

Camping equipment hire, Iceland

Kilometre 0

- *Products km 0 and turism, Es Pla, Mallorca*
- *Vinaròs Gastronómico, Castellón*

Mancomunidad Taula del Sénia (Valencia- Cataluña- Aragón)

*A governance structure encompassing
27 municipalities for the protection of
the heritage of
ancient olive trees*

**MANCOMUNITAT
TAULA del SÉNIA**

4theRegion, Bahía de Swansea, Gales

A platform for citizen dialogue on sustainable development in the region

Comuniterràe, Terre di Mezzo, Piamonte

*An Ecomuseum that seeks to ensure
that the life of Italian villages is not
lost to oblivion*

Cooperativa La Paranza, Nápoles

Social tourism venture seeking to employ young people from the Rione Sanità neighbourhood

CATA
COM
BEDI
NA
POLI

Alquiler de material de Camping Islandia, Reikiavik

Product-service model that rents high-quality equipment, reducing the level of waste in natural parks.

Km 0 y turismo, Es Pla, Mallorca

A network of producers who champion their uniqueness and generate value for the community.

Vinarós Gastronómico, Castellón

*A gastronomic identity and a commitment
between restaurants and local producers*

Need more inspiration?

Another examples that works

Ecobnb: “Airbnb” sustainable

Creation of a local trade network

Creation of a museum and links with other heritage sites

Collaboration with ecotourism companies in the region (e.g. Golnsitu)

Traditions and heritage, which are your resources: Carnival, Cattle Fair, White Night, oil production

Future of the town after reopening Tourist accommodation on offer

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Conclusions and next steps

And now?

After this meeting, how much closer do you feel to achieving your dream for your territory?

What challenges do you see ahead, and how can we work together?